

DERLEME

REVIEW

RENAL CELL CYTOTOXICITY AND ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY: A CLINICAL-BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF MARAS POWDER (SMOKELESS TOBACCO) INDUCED NEPHROTOXICITY IN THE EMERGENCY SETTING

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ABSTRACT

A male patient who presented to the Emergency Department of Karaman Training and Research Hospital exhibited significantly impaired renal function following the use of Maras Powder (a form of smokeless tobacco). This clinical observation is consistent with literature reports indicating that Maras Powder is a highly cytotoxic substance, a finding confirmed by in vitro toxicity studies conducted specifically on renal cell lines. The global use of this product is rapidly expanding, driven by its low cost, easy accessibility, and ability to be consumed without smoke, resulting in its use by younger demographics, including those at the middle school level. Maras Powder poses a serious threat to public health, leading users to seek clinical care for a wide variety of serious conditions, such as oral and dental health problems, peripheral circulatory disorders, cardiovascular issues, withdrawal syndrome, esophageal diseases, pregnancy complications, erectile dysfunction, cognitive decline, and hepatic and renal function impairment. This case underscores the escalating public health risk associated with Maras Powder consumption.

Keywords: Renal function, Maras powder, smokeless tobacco, emergency department, toxicity

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INTRODUCTION

Maras Powder is the most widely used smokeless tobacco product globally, and in Turkey, it is particularly prevalent in the Southeastern Anatolia region. It is also known by local names such as “Deli Tütün” (Crazy Tobacco) and “Ağızotu” (Mouth Herb). In both the pure form of Maras Powder and the form mixed with oak charcoal, concentrations of heavy metals, including aluminum, manganese, copper, zinc, and lead, are dangerously high for human health. It is important to raise public awareness regarding Maras Powder, which is often perceived as a less harmful and cheaper alternative to cigarettes (1). Although tobacco is most commonly consumed globally in the form of cigarettes, its direct smokeless use is quite widespread; there are approximately 288 million adult smokeless tobacco users in the Southeast Asia Region. This rate is stated to represent about 77% of the global total (2).

Maras Powder, the most common smokeless tobacco product in Turkey, is primarily consumed around Kahramanmaraş and Gaziantep, and its nicotine content is 6–10 times higher than that found in cigarettes (1, 3). Maras Powder is still often viewed as a seemingly innocuous addictive substance today; yet, its easy accessibility and high nicotine levels can cause severe toxicities, particularly for younger age groups. Containing significantly more nicotine than cigarettes, Maras Powder is an extremely harmful substance that, due to its oral placement, leads to decay, recession, loss of sensation, and cancer risk in the mouth, teeth, and gums (4). Once absorbed into the bloodstream, it causes blood pressure irregularities, vascular obstruction, risk of myocardial infarction, and generalized circulatory disorders. In males, it can cause impotence and erectile problems. In pregnant individuals, it may lead to severe outcomes such as miscarriage, premature birth, and intellectual and developmental delay in the infant. It inflicts extensive damage on the digestive system, including gastric and intestinal issues, extending to liver and kidney damage, and these effects are often irreversible (5, 6).

CASE PRESENTATION

A thirty-one-year-old male patient presented to the Emergency Department with complaints of right flank pain and generalized leg pain. The patient's general condition was good; he was cooperative and oriented. Physical examination findings were normal except for tenderness in the right costovertebral angle (CVA). The patient's vital signs were as follows: Blood pressure 160/110

mmHg (hypertension), oxygen saturation 96%, pulse 91/min, and temperature 36.1 °C. A detailed history revealed that the patient, who had no known chronic diseases, had been regularly using Maras Powder for the last five years. Laboratory tests detected significant renal failure and metabolic disturbance.

Table 1. Patient's Laboratory Values at the Time of Emergency Department Presentation

Parameter	Admission Value	Unit
Acid-Base Status		
pH (Arterial Blood Gas)	7.29	
HCO ₃ (Bicarbonate)	15.9	mmol/L
Renal and Electrolytes		
Urea (BUN)	224.7	mg/dL
Creatinine (Cr)	12.17	mg/dL
Ca (Calcium)	6.38	mg/dL
Enzymes and Metabolism		
CK (Creatine Kinase)	1286	U/L
Lactate	7.7	mmol/L
Hematology		
WBC (White Blood Cell)	7.13	K/ μ L
Hemoglobin (Hb)	12.1	g/dL
Platelet	159	K/ μ L

Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST), Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT), Sodium (Na), and Potassium (K) values were within normal limits. Urinalysis revealed proteinuria. An abdominal computed tomography (CT) scan performed showed the appearance of hypodense cysts in the right and left kidneys.

TREATMENT AND FOLLOW-UP

Upon detection of acute renal failure (AKI), significant metabolic acidosis, and rhabdomyolysis, the patient was admitted to the Internal Medicine Service with an indication for dialysis. Following dialysis, the patient's Creatine Kinase (CK) levels demonstrated a trend toward normalization, and a decrease in creatinine levels was observed. The patient was subsequently scheduled for regular dialysis sessions over a period of one month.

Figure 1. *Nicotiana Rustica* linn (Kahramanmaraş, Photo: Hale Koksoy Mi 10 lite Camera, 2018)

CELL CULTURE STUDIES

Maras Powder (*Nicotiana Rustica* derivatives) is a smokeless tobacco product with significant cytotoxic and systemic toxicity potential due to its high nicotine and alkaloid content. The nicotine concentration in *N. rustica* is reported to be approximately 10–20 times higher than that in commercial cigarette tobacco (3, 6). This increased nicotine level leads to toxic effects even at low doses in both clinical and experimental studies. In *in vitro* models (HK-2, HEK-293), Maras Powder extracts have been shown to significantly reduce cell viability at concentrations of 10–50 ppm. At concentrations of 100 ppm and higher, apoptosis emerged as the predominant mode of cell death, evidenced by increased caspase activity and nuclear changes detected by DAPI staining. The toxic ppm value of Maras Powder extracts can be determined by probit analysis (7). The same studies also reported changes in oxidative stress markers (MDA \uparrow , GSH \downarrow) and elevated expression of IL-6 and TNF- α , confirming that the observed toxicity develops via inflammation and oxidative stress pathways. These laboratory findings are consistent with the systemic toxicity profile observed clinically.

N. rustica exposure in living organisms is associated with severe effects such as acute cardiotoxicity, hypertension, arrhythmia, neurological symptoms, respiratory depression, and peripheral circulatory disorders (8–10). Because it can be consumed without smoke, high and continuous nicotine loading is particularly common in younger age groups, which consequently increases emergency department presentation rates. The most frequent symptoms of acute nicotine poisoning observed in patients admitted to the emergency department are tachycardia/bradycardia, hypertensive states, nausea and vomiting, dizziness, sweating, agitation, and, in severe cases, respiratory depression. In cases involving renal impairment, an increase in creatinine-urea and oliguria are notable findings. The immediate treatment approach is symptomatic, as there is no specific antidote. Patient's airway and circulatory stability must be ensured, IV fluid therapy should be initiated, atropine administered for bradycardia, and appropriate cardiovascular medications used for hypertension/tachycardia. If renal function impairment develops, fluid management and dialysis evaluation are essential. Both the clinical findings and the cellular level demonstration of increased oxidative stress and inflammatory response indicate that Maras Powder is more than just a local oral tobacco product; it is a serious public health concern leading to multi-organ toxicity (11, 12).

DISCUSSION

This case clearly demonstrates that the chronic use of Maras Powder can lead to severe organ system damage. The findings in the patient—high-grade hypertension (Blood Pressure: 160/110 mmHg), severe acute kidney injury (Creatinine: 12.17 mg/dL), metabolic acidosis (pH: 7.29), and rhabdomyolysis (CK: 1286 U/L)—strongly suggest the long-term systemic effects of nicotine toxicity or other toxic substances within the tobacco product. The renal damage may have been exacerbated by myoglobinuria resulting from rhabdomyolysis. Concurrently, severe hypocalcemia (Ca: 6.38 mg/dL) developed, likely due to phosphate release that frequently accompanies rhabdomyolysis. This case is one of the rare reported examples of Maras Powder (*Nicotiana rustica* Linn) toxicity in an adult patient, indicating that the product possesses a multifaceted toxicity profile attributable to its high nicotine content, alkaline composition, and heavy metals (such as copper and cadmium) carried by the wood ash component (12).

A study conducted on the oral mucosa examined genotoxic damage by performing micronucleus (MN) counts in a cohort of 100 subjects, divided into groups of conventional tobacco, reverse smoking, electronic cigarette, cannabis users, and non-smokers (n=20 in each group). Analysis results revealed that the MN count was significantly higher in conventional, reverse, and electronic cigarette users compared to the non-smoking control group ($P < 0.001$) (14). The high prevalence of smokeless tobacco use, reaching 2.4% of US adults (approximately 5.9 million people) and being particularly common among men, indicates that oral lesions and potential malignant transformation caused by these products threaten a large segment of the population. This wide usage underscores the necessity for dentists and physicians to increase their efforts in early diagnosis and management of such lesions (15). Smokeless tobacco is reported to harbor numerous chemical carcinogens, including tobacco-specific N-nitrosamines such as N'-nitrosonornicotine. These carcinogens have been linked to cancers of the oral cavity, esophagus, and stomach (16). In India, the widespread use of smokeless tobacco, encompassing approximately 21% of adults (with Khaini, a tobacco-lime mixture, being used by over 50%), highlights the product's impact on public health and the urgent need for regulation. It is noted that health warning labels on packages are often too small or absent (17). Furthermore, a comprehensive analysis was conducted by the Cross Cohort Collaboration Tobacco Working Group, harmonizing data from 15 prospective US cohorts spanning 1948–2015 to evaluate the long-term systemic risks of non-cigarette tobacco products. The

study examined the effects of non-cigarette tobacco use on significant cardiovascular outcomes, including myocardial infarction, stroke, heart failure, and atrial fibrillation. The median follow-up time of 13.8 years for all-cause mortality provides strong evidence for long-term risk assessment (18). In a reported case, the risk of acute nicotine toxicity associated with high-concentration nicotine pouches was clearly demonstrated. A 21-year-old male, who consumed 15 extra-strength nicotine pouches (10.9 mg of nicotine per pouch) over 12 hours while studying, presented to the emergency department with bizarre behavior, persistent confusion, and nausea. Although symptoms resolved within 24 hours, this case serves as an important warning that the ease of use and high nicotine content of these products can push users toward the threshold of acute toxicity, potentially necessitating emergency intervention, especially during periods of stress or dose escalation (19). In a separate context, clinical research on obesity has reported a 5–6% loss in patients' starting total body weight, alongside marked improvements in metabolic health indicators. Moreover, this process of weight management is suggested to enhance female fertility capacity by supporting conditions like Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) and endometriosis, and by concurrently reducing the drive for alcohol and smoking (20).

As confirmed by cell culture and cytotoxicity studies, Maras Powder extracts lead to significant cytotoxicity, increased oxidative stress, and activation of an inflammatory response in kidney cells, even at low doses (8, 9, 13). These experimental findings support the underlying cellular mechanisms responsible for the severe acute kidney injury (Creatinine: 12.17 mg/dL) observed in our patient. Clinically, acute nicotine poisoning can manifest as a wide spectrum of symptoms, including cardiovascular instability, neurological symptoms, and renal function impairment. This case report demonstrates that Maras Powder (*Nicotiana rustica* L.) use leads to a multifactorial systemic toxicity that cannot be attributed to a single mechanism due to its complex chemical components. The severe clinical picture observed in our patient (acute kidney injury, rhabdomyolysis, and metabolic acidosis) is closely linked not only to the high nicotine level but also to the product's overall chemical composition. The toxic profile of Maras Powder results from the simultaneous effects of three main components: high nicotine load, its alkaline pH composition, and its heavy metal content.

The significantly higher nicotine concentration in *N. rustica* compared to traditional tobacco types, combined with its prolonged contact with the oral mucosa (the traditional usage method), results

in rapid and high absorption (12). The pharmacological consequence of this is that nicotine triggers the release of catecholamines, leading to systemic vasoconstriction. This vasoconstriction and subsequent tissue hypoperfusion are the primary clinical mechanisms explaining the Type A Lactic Acidosis observed in our patient, indicated by a Lactate level of 7.70 mmol/L. The alkaline composition of the product (often derived from wood ash) not only facilitates nicotine absorption but also causes chemical irritation and increased permeability in the oral mucosa; the "burning sensation" reported by users is a clinical reflection of this effect (12). Additionally, heavy metals (specifically cadmium and copper) introduced to the product via the wood ash or absorbed by the plant are considered primary causes of long-term renal damage. In this context, the severe acute kidney injury observed in our patient (Creatinine: 12.17 mg/dL) is supported by in vitro (cell culture) studies (9, 13). These experimental findings definitively show that Maras Powder extracts have significant cytotoxic effects, particularly on renal tubular cells. Cytotoxicity is linked to oxidative stress, where components increase the production of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) within the cell, leading to lipid peroxidation. Furthermore, cytotoxic exposure activates transcription factors like NF- κ B, triggering an inflammatory response and inducing apoptosis (cell death) at high doses, contributing to the rapid deterioration of organ function (13).

Clinically detected rhabdomyolysis (CK: 1286 U/L) develops either from the direct toxic effect of high-dose nicotine and heavy metals on myocytes or from ischemic damage secondary to severe vasoconstriction. Myoglobinuria resulting from rhabdomyolysis exacerbates kidney damage, while hyperphosphatemia resulting from muscle damage and breakdown is the key physiopathological trigger leading secondarily to severe hypocalcemia (Ca: 6.38 mg/dL). The concordance of these comprehensive clinical and fundamental scientific findings indicates that the toxic effects of Maras Powder are robust, both experimentally and clinically. Early dialysis treatment is vital for patients with advanced renal damage, as observed in this case.

Clinicians should remain vigilant that Maras Powder use may be among the causes of unexplained hypertension, acute kidney failure, and rhabdomyolysis in young patients. For patients with advanced renal damage, as seen in this case, early dialysis treatment is vital. The consistent corroboration of cellular-level cytotoxic findings with the broad clinical picture observed in the emergency department demonstrates that the toxic effects of Maras Powder are robust both experimentally and clinically. This outcome reveals that Maras Powder possesses a multifactorial toxicity

profile stemming not only from nicotine but also from heavy metal content and chemical irritation linked to its alkaline pH. The complex toxicity profile demands that clinicians, particularly in regions where Maras Powder is prevalent, approach patients with a high degree of suspicion and take a detailed history. More comprehensive clinical and experimental studies are needed in this area to optimize the mechanisms of intoxication and treatment strategies. Overall, the molecular-level cytotoxic effects and the extensive clinical presentation observed in the emergency department reaffirm that Maras Powder poses a serious public health risk.

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